

Optimizing Load Management and Stability in Grid Connected Hybrid Renewable Energy Microgrid Systems using DPFC and Fuzzy Logic Controller for Electric Vehicle Charging

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KEYWORDS

Grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system (HRES), Distributed Power Flow Controller (DPFC), Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC), Electric Vehicle (EV) Charging, Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT), Perturb and Observe (P&O), Vehicle-to-Grid, Grid-to-Vehicle, Voltage Stability, Power Quality.

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel approach for optimizing load management and enhancing system stability in grid-connected hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES) using Distributed Power Flow Controllers (DPFC) and fuzzy logic controllers (FLC), with a focus on electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. The proposed system integrates solar and wind energy sources to supply power to both linear and nonlinear distribution loads, while also supporting bi-directional power flow for EV charging stations. The DPFC ensures precise control of active and reactive power, enabling efficient power flow management between the renewable sources, grid, and loads. To further improve system stability and performance, a fuzzy logic controller dynamically responds to fluctuations in power generation and demand, mitigating voltage instability and reducing harmonic distortion. Additionally, the Perturb and Observe (P&O) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) technique is employed to extract maximum power from the renewable energy sources under varying conditions. Simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed system in optimizing load distribution, maintaining stability, and enhancing the integration of renewable energy in grid-connected EV charging systems, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient energy infrastructure.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) in power systems has introduced significant challenges related to load management, stability, and power quality. Hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES), integrating solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind energy, have emerged as a sustainable solution for meeting the rising global electricity demand while reducing carbon emissions [1]. However, the intermittency and fluctuating nature of renewable energy sources pose difficulties in maintaining stable voltage and frequency profiles, especially in grid-connected electric vehicle (EV) charging systems [2]. The bidirectional power flow associated with EV charging and discharging further complicates the stability and control requirements of modern power networks [3]. To address these challenges, advanced power flow controllers and intelligent control strategies are required. Distributed Power Flow Controllers (DPFC) have gained prominence due to their ability to regulate active and reactive power independently, thereby enhancing grid stability and load management in HRES [4]. The DPFC, an advanced variant of the Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC), operates with multiple series converters, improving flexibility, efficiency, and reliability in power distribution networks [5]. In parallel, fuzzy logic controllers (FLC) have demonstrated superior performance in handling nonlinearities and uncertainties associated with power fluctuations in RES-integrated grids [6]. By dynamically adjusting control parameters, FLC enhances the stability of power systems and reduces total harmonic distortion (THD), ensuring efficient operation under varying load conditions [7]. Electric vehicle (EV) adoption has accelerated in recent years, leading to increased energy demand and new grid integration challenges [8]. The presence of EVs in a grid-connected HRES requires efficient energy management strategies to balance renewable generation, storage, and consumption dynamically [9]. The bidirectional nature of EV charging stations enables vehicle-to-grid (V2G) and grid-to-vehicle (G2V) operations, which can be leveraged to optimize energy distribution [10]. However, improper control mechanisms can lead to voltage instability, power losses, and harmonic distortions, necessitating advanced controllers such as DPFC and

FLC [11]. Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) techniques, such as the Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm, play a crucial role in ensuring optimal energy extraction from PV and wind sources under changing environmental conditions [12]. The implementation of P&O MPPT in the proposed system enhances the efficiency of power generation, thereby improving the overall performance of the grid-connected hybrid renewable system [13]. By integrating DPFC for precise power flow control and FLC for dynamic response to power fluctuations, the proposed system achieves enhanced voltage stability, reduced harmonics, and improved load distribution [14]. Several studies have explored the benefits of integrating DPFC and FLC in modern power networks. For instance, [15] investigated the role of DPFC in mitigating voltage instability in microgrid systems, while [16] demonstrated the effectiveness of FLC in reducing THD in hybrid power networks. Research conducted by [17] highlighted the importance of MPPT in optimizing renewable energy utilization, and [18] analyzed the impact of V2G technology in enhancing grid stability. Additionally, [19] and [20] presented case studies on real-world implementations of DPFC and FLC, validating their effectiveness in improving power quality and load management. In this study, a novel approach is proposed for optimizing load management and stability in a grid-connected HRES using DPFC and FLC for EV charging applications. The proposed system aims to regulate active and reactive power flow, mitigate voltage fluctuations, and ensure seamless energy integration between renewable sources, grid, and EVs. Simulation results demonstrate the system's ability to enhance power quality, maintain grid stability, and improve energy efficiency, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient energy infrastructure.

II. Proposed System Configuration

The proposed system integrates renewable energy sources like solar photovoltaic arrays and wind turbines into a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system (HRES) to support electric vehicle (EV) charging stations and local loads as shown in fig.1. The system is designed to ensure stable power delivery under varying environmental and load conditions while optimizing energy management through advanced power flow control strategies. A Distributed Power Flow Controller

(DPFC) is employed to regulate active and reactive power flow, enhancing voltage stability and reducing power losses. A Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) is integrated to enhance system stability, dynamically adjusting system parameters based on real-time fluctuations in power generation and load demand. The system operates in both Grid-to-Vehicle (G2V) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) modes, providing flexibility in power distribution. Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) using the Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm maximizes power extraction from solar and wind sources, improving overall system efficiency. The system is structured around three main subsystems: the renewable energy generation unit, the power control and management unit, and the EV charging infrastructure. The renewable generation unit converts variable DC power into a regulated DC output, while the power control and management unit distributes power

efficiently among grid loads, renewable sources, and EV chargers. The system's performance is simulated in MATLAB/Simulink, demonstrating its effectiveness in maintaining grid stability, optimizing power flow, and improving energy efficiency.

III. Modeling and designing of proposed system

A. Solar Power System

The solar power system plays a crucial role in optimizing load management and system stability in grid-connected hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES). The integration of solar photovoltaic (PV) generation with electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure requires efficient maximum power extraction, voltage regulation, and power flow control. This section provides a detailed solar PV model, MPPT techniques, power converters, and integration strategies for effective utilization in the proposed system.

FIG.1 Proposed system configuration

a. Solar PV System Modeling

A Photovoltaic (PV) system converts solar energy into electrical power using photovoltaic cells. The output power of a PV module depends on factors such as solar irradiance, temperature, and load conditions. The general mathematical model of a solar PV module is derived from the single-diode equivalent circuit and is expressed as:

Fig. 2 equivalent model of PV solar.

$$I = I_{ph} - I_o \left(e^{\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{nKT}} - 1 \right) - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- I_{ph} = Photogenerated current (dependent on solar irradiance and temperature)
- I_o = Reverse saturation current
- q = Electron charge (1.6×10^{-19} C)
- V = PV module output voltage
- I = PV module output current
- R_s = Series resistance of the PV cell
- R_{sh} = Shunt resistance of the PV cell
- n = Ideality factor of the diode
- K = Boltzmann's constant (1.38×10^{-23} J/K)
- T = Temperature in Kelvin

B. Solar PV Boost Converter with P&O MPPT Algorithm

A solar PV boost converter with a Perturb and Observe (P&O) MPPT algorithm is designed to maximize power extraction from a photovoltaic (PV) panel while ensuring the output voltage is suitable for the connected load or battery as shown in Fig.3. The PV panel generates DC electricity, but its output varies with irradiance and temperature, requiring an MPPT controller to operate at the Maximum Power Point (MPP). A boost converter, consisting of an inductor, MOSFET switch, diode, and capacitor, is used to step up the PV voltage. When the MOSFET switch is ON, the inductor stores energy from the PV panel, and when the MOSFET is OFF, the inductor releases energy to the output, thereby increasing the voltage.

The output voltage (V_o) is controlled by adjusting the duty cycle (D) using the relation

$$V_o = V_{pv} / (1 - D) \quad (2)$$

The P&O MPPT algorithm works by continuously perturbing the PV voltage and observing the resulting power change. It first measures the PV voltage (V_{pv}) and current (I_{pv}), then calculates the power (P_{pv}). If a small increase in voltage leads to an increase in power, the algorithm continues perturbing in the same direction; otherwise, it reverses the perturbation to reach the MPP. This iterative process ensures that the PV panel operates at its highest efficiency. The combination of the boost converter and P&O MPPT controller effectively regulates the PV output, improving energy harvesting efficiency and providing a stable power supply for various applications.

Fig. 3 solar PV P&O MPPT DC-DC boost converter

C. Perturb and Observe (P&O) MPPT Algorithm

The Perturb and Observe (P&O) Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm is one of the most widely used techniques for optimizing the power output from a solar photovoltaic (PV) system. The power generated by a PV panel depends on environmental conditions such

as solar irradiance and temperature, making it necessary to continuously track the Maximum Power Point (MPP) for efficient operation as shown in Fig.4. The P&O algorithm operates by making small perturbations (incremental changes) to the PV voltage (V_{pv}) and observing the resulting changes in power (P_{pv}). Based on this observation, the algorithm decides whether to continue perturbing in the same direction or to reverse the perturbation to ensure that the system remains near the MPP. The working can be summarized as follows:

1. Measure the PV voltage (V_{pv}) and current (I_{pv}), then compute the power:

$$P_{pv} = V_{pv} \times I_{pv} \quad (3)$$

2. Compare the new power value with the previous power value ($P_{pv}(n)$ and $P_{pv}(n-1)$):

- If $P_{pv}(n) > P_{pv}(n-1)$, it means the system is moving towards the MPP, so the voltage perturbation is maintained in the same direction.
- If $P_{pv}(n) < P_{pv}(n-1)$, it indicates that the system has moved away from the MPP, so the voltage perturbation direction is reversed.

Fig. 4 flow chart of P&O MPPT algorithm

The process continues iteratively to keep the system at or near the maximum power point. The decision-making process of the P&O algorithm is expressed as:

$$\text{if } dP_{pv}/dV_{pv} > 0 \rightarrow \text{increase } v_{pv} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{if } dP_{pv}/dV_{pv} < 0 \rightarrow \text{decrease } v_{pv} \quad (5)$$

Where

$$dP_{pv} = P_{pv}(n) - p_{pv}(n-1) \quad (6)$$

$$dV_{pv} = V_{pv}(n) - V_{pv}(n-1) \quad (7)$$

The duty cycle (D) of the boost converter is adjusted accordingly to ensure the operating point moves toward the MPP. The duty cycle is updated as:

$$D(n) = D(n - 1) \pm \Delta D \quad (8)$$

Where ΔD is the perturbation step size.

D. Bidirectional Buck-Boost Converter for EV Charging in DC Microgrid

The bidirectional buck-boost converter plays a crucial role in managing energy flow between the battery energy storage system (BESS) and the DC bus in a microgrid. This converter enables both charging and discharging of the battery, ensuring stable power delivery for electric vehicle (EV) charging. In buck mode, the converter steps down the DC bus voltage to charge the battery, while in boost mode, it steps up the battery voltage to supply power to the microgrid or EV load as shown in Fig.5. The control strategy dynamically adjusts the duty cycle to regulate power flow efficiently. The converter also helps stabilize the DC bus voltage, mitigating fluctuations from intermittent renewable energy sources like solar and wind. The energy management strategy ensures optimal charging and discharging cycles, enhancing battery lifespan and overall system efficiency.

Fig.5

principle operation bidirectional dc-dc buck boost converter

1. Buck Mode (Battery Charging)

Output Voltage in Buck Mode:

$$V_b = D \cdot V_{dc} \quad (9)$$

Where: V_b = Battery voltage, V_{dc} = DC bus voltage, D = Duty cycle ($0 < D < 1$)

Inductor Current Ripple in Buck Mode:

$$\Delta I_L = \frac{(1-D)V_{dc}}{L f_s} \quad (10)$$

Where: ΔI_L = Inductor current ripple, L = Inductor value, f_s = Switching frequency

2. Boost Mode (Battery Discharging)

Output Voltage in Boost Mode:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{V_b}{1-D} \quad (11)$$

Inductor Current Ripple in Boost Mode:

$$\Delta I_L = \frac{D V_b}{L f_s} \quad (12)$$

E. Double-Loop Controller for EV Charging System

The control strategy for electric vehicle (EV) charging involves a double-loop control system to ensure efficient, stable, and safe charging as shown in Fig.6. The outer voltage loop maintains a constant DC bus voltage, while the inner current loop regulates the battery charging current. A Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is used in both loops to minimize steady-state error and improve dynamic performance.

Fig. 6 double loop ev charging controller

1. Outer Voltage Loop: DC Bus Voltage Control

The outer voltage loop ensures the DC bus voltage (V_{dc}) remains stable and within the desired range. Since variations in EV charging loads and grid fluctuations affect the DC bus voltage, this loop provides a reference current (I_{ev}^*) for the inner current loop.

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_v(t) = V_{dc}^* - V_{dc} \quad (13)$$

PI Controller Output (Reference EV Charging Current I_{ev}^*)

$$I_{ev}^*(t) = K_{pv} e_v(t) + k_{iv} \int e_v(t) dt \quad (14)$$

Where: I_{ev}^* = Reference charging current for the inner loop, K_{pv} = Proportional gain of voltage controller, K_{iv} = Integral gain of voltage controller

This reference current is then passed to the inner current loop for precise battery charging control.

2. Inner Current Loop: Battery Current Control

The inner current loop ensures the EV battery is charged with a smooth and regulated current to prevent over current issues and battery degradation. The PI controller in this loop generates the duty cycle for the DC-DC converter (buck or boost).

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_i(t) = I_{ev}^* - I_{ev} \quad (15)$$

PI Controller Output (Duty Cycle Control)

$$D(t) = K_{pi} e_i(t) + k_{ii} \int e_i(t) dt \quad (16)$$

Where: D = Duty cycle of the DC-DC converter, K_{pi}= Proportional gain of current controller, K_{ii}= Integral gain of current controller

This duty cycle (D) is applied to the DC-DC converter, adjusting the output voltage and current to regulate battery charging.

IV. Wind Power Conversion System

A. Modeling and Designing of a Self-Excited Induction Generator (SEIG)

The Self-Excited Induction Generator (SEIG) is widely used in standalone and grid-connected renewable energy systems, particularly in wind and micro-hydro applications as shown in fig.7. In your system, SEIG is integrated with solar PV and electric vehicle (EV) charging, requiring efficient voltage regulation, reactive power compensation, and power flow management.

1. Working Principle of SEIG

A squirrel cage Induction Generator (SCIG) operates based on the principle of self-excitation, where capacitors provide the necessary reactive power to build up the voltage. Unlike synchronous generators, SCIGs do not require an external excitation source, making them suitable for remote and hybrid renewable systems. When a prime mover (such as a wind turbine or hydro turbine) rotates the SEIG at a speed higher than synchronous speed, the residual magnetism in the rotor induces a small voltage in the stator windings. The connected capacitor bank then sustains and boosts the voltage, allowing continuous generation.

Fig. 7 wind conversion converter topology

2. Mathematical Modeling of SCIG

The mathematical model of an SEIG is based on the steady-state and dynamic equations governing voltage build-up, magnetization, and power flow.

2.1 Stator Voltage Equations

The voltage equations for an SEIG in a stationary dq-reference frame are:

$$V_d = R_s I_d + \frac{d\lambda_d}{dt} - \omega_s \lambda_q$$

$$V_q = R_s I_q + \frac{d\lambda_q}{dt} + \omega_s \lambda_d$$

where:

- V_d, V_q = Stator voltages in dqdqdq frame
- I_d, I_q = Stator currents
- R_s = Stator resistance
- λ_d, λ_q = Stator flux linkages
- ω_s = Synchronous speed of SCIG

2.2 Rotor Flux Linkages

The rotor flux linkages are given by:

$$\lambda_d = L_m I_{r_d} + L_s I_d$$

$$\lambda_q = L_m I_{r_q} + L_s I_q$$

where:

- L_m = Magnetizing inductance
- L_s = Stator self-inductance
- I_{rd}, I_{rq} = Rotor currents in dq frame

2.3 Magnetization Characteristics

The magnetizing reactance X_m is a nonlinear function of stator voltage:

$$X_m = f(V_s)$$

Since the voltage build-up depends on residual magnetism, the magnetizing reactance changes dynamically. The SEIG operates stably when the excitation capacitors provide sufficient reactive power to maintain the voltage.

3. Excitation and Reactive Power Compensation

Since SEIG cannot generate reactive power, a capacitor bank is used to provide self-excitation and voltage regulation. The required excitation capacitance C_{ex} is determined by:

where: Q = Reactive power demand, ω = Angular frequency, V = Generated voltage

Capacitor Selection for SEIG

- **Undersized capacitors** → Voltage collapse due to insufficient reactive power.

- **Oversized capacitors** → Overvoltage issues and excessive magnetizing currents.

To ensure proper excitation, the capacitance should be selected based on load conditions and wind speed variations.

V. CONTROL OF UPQC

The UPQC-PV-WE-ESS system integrates renewable energy sources with cutting-edge methods for monitoring power quality. The reduction of voltage issues such as sags, swells, harmonics, and flickers enhances grid reliability and system efficiency. Combining the shunt and series compensator characteristics of the UPQC, this design maximizes its possibilities. One way shunt compensators deal with power quality issues, such reactive power and load current harmonics, is by dynamically changing compensation currents. It facilitates the integration of renewable energy sources by collecting solar radiation and transforming wind energy into useful power. In order to protect the load from low-quality grid power, the series compensator injects appropriate voltages in phase with the grid voltage. The system's integration of energy storage also increases grid reliability, provides backup power in the event of grid failures, and strengthens the energy system as a whole. The UPQC-PV-WE-ESS system regulates the DC-link voltage at the generated reference using a proportional-integral (PI) controller, as shown in Figure 8, to correct for the load current using the Selective Harmonic Reduction Factor (SRF) approach. By converting load currents into the d-q-0 domain using phase-locked loop (PLL) data, precise grid synchronization may be achieved. To maintain system responsiveness with little impact on dynamic performance, we use a moving average filter (MAF). Ultimately, the UPQC-PV-WE-ESS system effectively addresses power quality issues, integrates renewable energy sources, and constructs a more resilient and environmentally friendly energy future.

A. Control of Shunt Compensator

Phase voltages are calculated by dividing line voltage by the square root of three, which accurately determines the voltage supplied to each phase in a three-phase power system. This method accounts for the phase shift

between line and phase voltages, ensuring efficient operation for each phase.

$$V_a = \frac{1}{3}(2V_{ab} + V_{bc}) \quad (17)$$

$$V_b = \frac{1}{3}(-V_{ab} + V_{bc}) \quad (18)$$

$$V_c = \frac{1}{3}(-V_{ab} - 2V_{bc}) \quad (19)$$

The terminal voltage V_t is derived from phase voltages as,

$$V_t = \sqrt{(2(V_a^2 + V_b^2 + V_c^2) / 3)} \quad (20)$$

DC Loss Component Estimation

The sensed DC link voltage (V_{dc}) is compared with the DC link reference voltage ($V_{dc\ ref}$) and the difference in voltage (V_{dce}) is acquired.

$$V_{dce}(n) = V_{dcref}(n) - V_{dc}(n) \quad (21)$$

The error is fed to the DC link voltage controller for minimization. The controller is governed as,

$$w_{loss}(n) = w_{loss}(n-1) + k_{il}\{V_{dce}(n) - V_{dce}(n-1)\} + k_{pl}\{V_{dce}(n)\} \quad (22)$$

Where, k_{il} and k_{pl} are the controller gains.

Estimation of Feed-Forward Components of RERs

Making use of the feed-forward terms linked to the RERs improves the dynamic responsiveness. To determine the RER feed-forward terms, one must do the following:

$$I_{PVg} = \frac{2P_{PV}}{3V_t} \quad (23)$$

$$I_{wind} = \frac{2P_{wind}}{3V_t} \quad (24)$$

Where P_{PV} and I_{PVg} represent PV power and its feed-forward term, P_{wind} and I_{wind} stand for wind power and its feed-forward term, respectively.

$$MAF(s) = \frac{1-e^{-T_w s}}{T_w s} \quad (25)$$

Eliminating harmonics from the current element on the d-axis is a crucial function of the Moving Average Filter (MAF). By adjusting its window length to half of the fundamental time period, we may remove harmonics without affecting the fundamental frequency component. The component of fundamental frequency stays the same due to its DC gain of one. To get rid of higher-order harmonics, however, we dampen integer multiples of the window depth. Maximizing the power extraction from the PV array and wind output, as well as improving power quality and performance, are all

dependent on a control system that has been carefully built and tuned. An important part of this system is the equivalent current component that is generated by the wind and PV array.

$$I_{sd}^* = I_{Ldf} + I_{loss} - I_{pv} - I_{wg} \quad (26)$$

The currents in the abc domain reference grid are transformed from I_{sd}^* . In order to provide the gating pulses for the shunt converter, a hysteresis current controller compares the reference grid currents with the measured grid currents.

Fig. 8. Control Structure of Shunt Compensator

B. Designing for series converter controller

The series converter is designed to enhance power quality in grid-connected systems by mitigating voltage disturbances such as sags, swells, and harmonics. As a key component of the Dynamic Voltage Restorer (DVR), the series converter operates by injecting compensating voltage into the grid to maintain a stable power supply for critical loads as shown in fig.9. The series converter adjusts its operation based on real-time voltage fluctuations at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC). It continuously measures the grid voltage and injects the required compensating voltage using a predefined reference-based method. The system operates by directly sensing voltage variations and using pulse width modulation (PWM) techniques to regulate the injected voltage. The injected voltage is derived from real-time

grid conditions, ensuring that voltage sags and swells are automatically corrected. To minimize harmonic distortion and maintain a sinusoidal voltage waveform, the series converter incorporates passive filtering techniques such as LC filters or transformer-based isolation to smooth the injected voltage. As solar power generation varies, the series converter dynamically adjusts the compensating voltage based on the available power from the photovoltaic (PV) system. This ensures that the load receives a constant and stable voltage supply, regardless of fluctuations in the grid. By eliminating the need for complex control mechanisms, the proposed system simplifies operation while still achieving effective voltage regulation and harmonic suppression, ensuring high power quality in renewable energy-integrated grid systems.

Fig.9 Series converter controller

VI. Grid Connected Hybrid Renewable Energy Microgrid Systems

A bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) plays a crucial role in integrating renewable energy systems, electric vehicle charging stations, and microgrids by enabling efficient power exchange between the grid and the DC link as shown in Fig.10. The d-q current control strategy is widely used to regulate power flow, improve power quality, and maintain DC link voltage stability. The system operates under a synchronous reference frame (SRF) to ensure precise control of active and reactive power components. The hierarchical structure of the control operation of the grid-connected bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) includes regulating the DC-link voltage, controlling the current, synchronizing the grid, and managing the bidirectional power flow. An outer-loop PI controller regulates the DC-link voltage by modifying the d-axis current reference (I_{d_ref}), which maintains the reference DC voltage.

Fig.10 designing of bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter

This keeps the DC bus steady, which is important for the DC load's efficient power exchange with the grid. To provide fine-grained control over active and reactive power, the currents on the d- and q-axes are regulated by the inner-loop current controllers such that they follow their respective reference values (P-Q regulation). In order to keep the converter running smoothly regardless of changes to the grid, as shown in Figure 11, grid

synchronization using a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) is necessary. Depending on the direction of power flow, the bidirectional functioning of the converter enables a smooth transition between rectifier mode, which charges from the grid to DC, and inverter mode, which discharges DC from the grid. The converter maintains the necessary DC voltage by drawing power from the grid in rectifier mode, and when there is surplus DC power, it injects electricity back into the grid in inverter mode. Optimal power management, improved grid stability, and increased system efficiency are all outcomes of an all-encompassing control method.

1. Mathematical Modeling of the Bidirectional AC-DC VSC

The operation of the bidirectional VSC can be described using d-q axis equations derived from Kirchhoff's Voltage Law (KVL). The system consists of an LC filter, a three-phase inverter, and a DC-link capacitor, ensuring stable voltage conversion.

1.1 AC Side d-q Equations

The AC-side dynamics of the three-phase VSC in the synchronous rotating reference frame are given by:

$$V_d = R_s I_d + L_s \frac{dI_d}{dt} - \omega L_s I_q + V_{gd} \quad (18)$$

$$V_q = R_s I_q + L_s \frac{dI_q}{dt} - \omega L_s I_d + V_{gq} \quad (19)$$

where:

- V_d, V_q = d-q axis voltages at the converter terminals
- I_d, I_q = d-q axis currents
- R_s, L_s = Resistance and inductance of the filter
- ω = Synchronous angular frequency
- V_{gd}, V_{gq} = d-q components of the grid voltage

The active power (P) and reactive power (Q) injected into the grid are given by:

$$P = \frac{3}{2} (V_d I_d + V_q I_q) \quad (20)$$

decisions into actionable commands, such as adjusting a motor speed or setting a temperature.

- e. **Output:** The defuzzified output is used to adjust the system's variables, such as controlling a motor's speed or regulating the temperature.

Fig. 12. Schematic diagram of Vdc controller.

Fuzzy controls are straightforward. Input, processing, and output. The input stage maps sensors, switches, thumbwheels, etc. to membership functions and truth values. The processing stage invokes each rule, generates a result for each, and combines the results. The output stage translates the combined result into a control output. Most membership functions are triangular, but trapezoidal and bell curves are also employed. The shape is less significant than the quantity and positioning of curves.

Fig.8 Example figures of input and output membership functions

Fuzzy control system design is based on empirical methods, basically A methodical approach to trial and-error. The general process is as follows:

- Document the system's operational specifications and inputs and outputs.
- Document the fuzzy sets for the inputs.
- Document the rule set.
- Determine the defuzzification method.
- Run through test suite to validate system, adjust details as required.
- Complete document and release to production.

This mechanism is divided into three parts. First, using input membership functions the inputs are fuzzified and then based on rule bases and inference system, outputs are produced and finally the fuzzy outputs are defuzzified and applied to the system. Error and the error change rate are selected as inputs. The block diagram of fuzzy control is represented as follows:

Table 1 :Inference matrix

$e \dot{e}$	NB	NS	Z	PS	PB
NB	NB	NB	NB	NS	Z
NS	NB	NB	NS	Z	PS
Z	NB	NS	Z	PS	PB
PS	NS	Z	PS	PB	PB
PB	Z	PS	PB	PB	PB

Fig 13 Surface generated by the fuzzy system
Generally, the design of a fuzzy controller for the control of electric drives requires the choice of the following parameters: linguistic variables, membership functions, inference method, and defuzzification strategy. Fuzzy

controller inputs are the error and its derivative, while the output is the command itself. Triangular and trapezoidal membership functions are used on a universe of discourse normalized in the range [-1; 1] for each variable as shown in Fig.8 respectively for the inputs (error, error variation) and output (input process). The subsets fuzzy membership were noted as follows: NB: Negative-Big; NS: Negative-Small; Z: Zero; PS: Positive-Small; PB:Positive-Big. The fuzzy rules, for determining output variable of the controller as a function of input variables are grouped in the Table 1. The simulation results for Optimizing Load Management and Stability in Grid Connected Hybrid Renewable Energy Microgrid Systems using DPFC and Fuzzy Logic Controller for Electric Vehicle Charging presented in this section. Both configurations described in section II are considered in the single-phase case: a grid-connected BESS that takes advantage of the EV buck-boost capabilities; and a hybrid grid connected PV-EV system that provides consistent power to the grid while using the battery as an energy buffer. The three-phase instance, on the other hand, investigates a hybrid system with two dc sources and an ac load.

VIII. Results and Discussion

A. Analysis of Grid-Connected HRES with DPFC and FLC Control

The grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system (HRES) integrating solar photovoltaic (PV), wind energy, and a self-excited induction generator (SEIG) was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink to assess its effectiveness in optimizing power flow, voltage stability, and EV charging performance as shown in fig.14. The system was tested under dynamic load conditions and varying renewable generation profiles, ensuring its capability to maintain stable operation under real-world scenarios. The solar PV array was subjected to varying solar irradiance levels, and the P&O Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm successfully adjusted the duty cycle of the DC-DC boost converter to track the maximum power point (MPP). Similarly, the wind turbine with SEIG operated under fluctuating wind speeds, and the power output was regulated to match the grid and load demand. The bidirectional converter enabled smooth transitions between Grid-to-Vehicle (G2V) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) modes, effectively balancing the power flow between the grid, renewable

sources, and EV batteries. The impact of Distributed Power Flow Controller (DPFC) and Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) on grid voltage stability was analyzed by comparing system performance with and without controllers. Without the proposed controllers, significant voltage fluctuations and harmonic distortions were observed, particularly during EV charging events and sudden variations in renewable power generation. However, with DPFC and FLC, the system achieved enhanced voltage stability, optimized reactive power compensation, and a significant reduction in Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) from 2.74% to 0.9%. The DPFC efficiently managed active and reactive power flow, preventing overload conditions and improving overall grid performance. Further analysis of EV charging profiles showed effective power management, with the State of Charge (SOC) of EV batteries increasing smoothly during G2V operation and discharging efficiently during V2G operation to support grid stability. The controllers ensured efficient power distribution, reducing the risk of voltage sags during high-demand conditions. The results also indicated that the charging and discharging cycles of EVs were efficiently regulated, preventing unnecessary energy losses. Overall, the simulation results validate the effectiveness of the proposed DPFC and FLC-based control strategy in enhancing power quality, voltage stability, and renewable energy utilization in a grid-connected HRES. The system successfully maintained stable operation under varying load and generation conditions, demonstrating its potential for real-world implementation in modern renewable energy-based EV charging infrastructures.

Fig.14 Simulation Results and Analysis of Grid-Connected HRES with DPFC and FLC Control
B. Dynamic Power Management in Microgrid-Connected HRES

The simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of dynamic power management in a microgrid-connected hybrid renewable energy system (HRES) under varying climatic conditions as shown in fig.15. The system, comprising solar PV, a squirrel cage induction generator (SCIG) for wind power, and an EV battery, efficiently balances power supply and demand. Initially, from 0 to 0.25 seconds, the solar PV system operates under standard irradiance (1000 W/m^2), providing stable power generation, with the grid and EV battery remaining in standby mode as the renewable power is sufficient to meet the 30 kW load demand. Between 0.25 and 0.45 seconds, the wind energy system (SCIG) starts generating power, supplementing solar power, and reducing the grid's contribution. However, from 0.45 to 0.7 seconds, the wind speed begins to decrease, leading to a corresponding drop in wind power output, requiring the grid to compensate for the power deficit. Further, between 0.7 and 0.8 seconds, solar irradiance decreases from 1000 W/m^2 to 500 W/m^2 , causing a reduction in PV power output, prompting an increased grid contribution to maintain load stability. Finally, from 0.8 to 1 second, the EV battery discharges at 50A, actively participating in load balancing by supplying power, which reduces the grid's power contribution and helps stabilize voltage and frequency. Throughout the simulation, the proposed system efficiently manages fluctuating power generation and dynamic load variations, ensuring a stable and reliable power supply for both linear and non-linear loads while optimizing grid, renewable energy, and EV battery contributions.

FIG.15 Simulation results for Dynamic Power Management in Microgrid-Connected HRES

C. DPFC-Based Voltage Sag and Swell Compensation

The simulation results validate the effectiveness of the Distributed Power Flow Controller (DPFC) in mitigating voltage sag and swell conditions, thereby improving the power quality of the load supply as shown in fig.16. Voltage sag occurs between 0.2 and 0.4 seconds due to a sudden increase in load demand or a temporary fault in the system. During this period, the DPFC injects the necessary compensating voltage to restore the grid voltage, ensuring uninterrupted and stable power delivery to the connected loads. Similarly, a voltage swell is observed between 0.6 and 0.8 seconds, caused by a reduction in load demand or a sudden power injection from renewable sources. The DPFC effectively absorbs the excess voltage and stabilizes the grid supply, preventing potential overvoltage issues. Throughout the simulation, the DPFC successfully maintains a balanced voltage profile, reducing fluctuations and enhancing power quality, ensuring a stable and reliable power supply for both linear and nonlinear loads.

Fig. 16 Simulation results for sag and swell condition

D. THD Comparison Using Fuzzy and PI Controllers

The simulation results clearly highlight the advantages of employing a fuzzy logic controller over a conventional PI controller in the proposed grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system as shown in fig.17. When operating under the fuzzy logic control scheme, the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) in the grid current is significantly reduced to 3.44%, and the microgrid current THD is maintained at 3.09%. In contrast, under PI controller operation, the grid current THD rises to 5.01%, while the microgrid current THD slightly increases to 3.34%. Notably, the load current THD remains consistent at 25.57% in both cases, indicating the nonlinear nature of the load and the limited influence of the control strategy on the load side. These findings demonstrate that the fuzzy controller provides better harmonic mitigation on the grid and microgrid sides, enhancing power quality and contributing to improved system stability under dynamic load and generation conditions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Fig.17 (a&d) Micro grid current THD, (b&e) grid current THD, (c&f) Load Current THD

Conclusion

This paper presented a novel grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system (HRES) integrating solar PV, wind energy, and electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. The proposed system utilized a Distributed Power Flow Controller (DPFC) for active and reactive power regulation and a Fuzzy Logic Controller (FLC) to enhance system stability and power quality. The bidirectional power flow capability in EV charging stations was leveraged for Grid-to-Vehicle (G2V) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) operations, ensuring efficient energy distribution. Simulation results demonstrated that the proposed system effectively optimized load distribution, reduced voltage fluctuations, and minimized harmonic distortion, contributing to improved power quality and grid stability. The integration of Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) using the Perturb and Observe (P&O) algorithm enhanced renewable energy utilization, ensuring maximum power extraction from solar and wind sources under dynamic environmental conditions. The proposed approach successfully addressed key challenges in HRES, including voltage instability, power losses, and load balancing, making it a viable solution for modern smart grids and sustainable EV charging infrastructure. Future research can explore adaptive and AI-based control techniques to further optimize power flow and improve system resilience under extreme load variations and environmental uncertainties.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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